

Virtues in Hausa Verse: An Examination of Humility and Modesty

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Abstract

Virtue is the best and right passions and actions of an individual. Humility and modesty are the chief characteristics of Hausa culture that keeps one from immorality in what to see, say, listen, taste, how to dress, treat people and where to go. Humility and modesty in Hausa are attributed to strong faith to the oneness of God and the total submission to his will as well as following Prophetic teachings and doing well to oneself via interaction with others. The corpus poems described mutual relationship between humility and modesty and elaborate that, humility and modesty required self-awareness and open-mindedness among other virtues, for a benevolent to be considered humble and modest. The paper exposed arrogant royal regalia and the procession to Hausa monarch of the pre-jihad and after. The verse called for replacement of vices with good and noble virtues (humility and modesty). The research adopted empirical method while choosing poems and relies solely on secondary data for analyzing poems. The paper portrayed comprehensive account on humility and modesty in select Hausa verse, whereby poets' erudition and self-incrimination serve as a method of guiding humanity to moral values, and admonished the populace to be humble and modest to God and present self-discipline in decorous language while interacting with others. The poets apply the value of identities, strengths and limitations of their selves to eradicate pride by persistence on self-criticism and by criticizing evil acts in the society. This research would benefit scholars, administrators, leaders, followers and humanitarians, it would be valuable also to philosophers, anthropologists, sociologists, historians and other related disciplines.

INTRODUCTION

Virtue is a good character displayed consciously or unconsciously while interacting with people. Humility and modesty are closely related though humility is the ability to appreciate goodness in others while modesty avoids vices and exemplifies goodness. Both terms are virtues of the benevolent that awareness and open-mindedness guide their obedient to God and his messenger, to appreciate others and been free from arrogance and boastfulness. The corpus of this paper is a compendium of humility and modesty because it exemplifies modesty to the God and within the people. The incorporation of awareness and open-mindedness to humility and modesty as well as the significance of Islam to humility and modesty manifested in the corpus poems as the review of literature on *mutumin kirki* and *nagari na kowa* indicates other virtues that motivate the mind of the benevolent to be good. In addition, parents, Qur'anic school and other genres of Hausa literature introduced moral values to Hausa children. The paper examines virtues in Hausa verse and restricts itself to humility and modesty and then looks into the incorporation of self-awareness and open-mindedness among other virtues to humility and modesty. Moral development is obvious in the written poetry of 19th, 20th to 21st centuries in Hausaland due to Islamic influence on Hausa culture followed by the jihad of Uthman Bin Fodio and the establishment of Sokoto Caliphate and beyond.

VIRTUES IN HAUSA TRADITION AND OTHER CULTURES

Aristotle (2006) defines virtue as a mean to what is best and right, it is also concerns passions and actions. Blackburn (2008), Aristotle (2006) and Rachels (2006) explain that, the greater soul possessed by the benevolent made them virtuous, utilitarian and source of happiness to others. The writers add that virtue comprises benevolence, civility, compassion,

conscientiousness, cooperativeness, courage, courteousness, dependability, fairness, friendliness, generosity, honesty, industriousness, justice, loyalty, moderation, reasonableness, self-confidence, self-control, self-discipline, tactfulness, thoughtfulness, tolerance, humility, charity, patience and chastity etc. In addition, Virtue according to these philosophers qualifies the virtuous better either morally or intellectually. Blackburn (2008) adds that, virtue distinguishes interest of its possessor, differs from culture to culture, generation to generation and within the philosophers. Blackburn (2008) says that, virtue ethics concerns on virtue than describing goodness of virtue but the theory gives priority to the consequences or motive of virtue because virtue is a conduct of individual mind that has value as it renders happiness within a culture or people. Virtue epistemology according to Blackburn (2008) investigates and validates the foundation of culture (belief) on virtues, it studies similarities of right attitudes and moral values within a culture and justifies epistemic virtues.

Daud, Ogunbado, and Ahmed, (2016) overview the etymology of the word ethics from *ethos*; means habit and custom while moral from *moralis/moralitas*; means mores and custom in the Latin. They further say that ethics consists of duties of a man, his attitudes, and the virtues of the individual in a given society. In other words, ethics as a branch of philosophy studies the principles and concept of morality, foundation of morality, status of justification of moral rules, the relationship between moral and other human objectives and the nature of responsibility. The writers argue that ethics is alternate to morality while personality deals with characteristics and behavior displayed consciously or unconsciously by human beings in his daily interactions.

Zhang, Lic, and Liang, (2016) say humility in the Western culture originated from Latin word *humus/humi* means *on the ground* or *earth* while in the Eastern culture means *modesty* or *not conceited*. Furthermore, the writers describe people with humility in the two cultures as those who believe in their mind that they are in the bottom while humility in academic point of view is the ability and quality of human attitudes and character that one sets to determine his identities, strengths and limitations in relationship with other people. Hung, Huang, and Chiu, (2012) view humility as a well-recognized virtue but they say the society has neglected because it is regarded a waste of time for a society to succeed in humility. The writers also add that modesty, humble, and self-affecting are synonyms with humility and traditional Chinese culture appreciate humility above all cultures because it elevates who are contented and humble to the heaven and people who know how to attract self-discipline and humility are respected because it denigrates boastfulness and learn to be humble and strive on humility as a virtue. Humility in the Western culture is associated with reputation and success of an individual; it is also in collaboration with self-awareness, openness, transcendence, sincerity, fairness, open-mindedness, respectfulness of other people and avoidance of arrogance, egotism and conceit. Humility is a unique attitude that can be learnt as other virtues within a long period.

Daud, Ogunbado, and Ahmed, (2016) explain that human personality development in Islam relies on serviceable knowledge as stated in the first revelation in the Qur'an and the virtues of knowledgeable is greater as it elevates their personality to value the concept of justice and stand on it firmly. The writers explicate that the gradual process of revelation of the Qur'an was for the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) and his companions to memorize, understand and internalize the message in daily life. In addition, Islam guides Muslims to improve their relationship with Allah as their creator in many ways, they should also be simple, modest and humble to themselves and they should be in harmony with humanity.

Muhammad (1997) says virtue is required in building humanity and honesty should be at the center, great men like late Ibrahim Yaro Yahaya are the pillar to build humanity due to that gaskiya truth, *aminci* reliability, *dɛmbin alheri* so much kindness, *alkawari* promise, *hakuri* patience, *amana* trust, *adali* just, *kwazo* deligence and *kin nuna bambanci* equality. The writer

describes late Ibrahim Yaro Yahaya as having *nagarta* goodness, *kuzari* energetic, *lafiyar zuciya da ta jiki* good mind and healthy body, *yawan walwala, fara*, shining face, *barkwanci* joking, *'yangaranci* worldly wisdom, *zurfin tunani* good reasoning, *kishin al'umma* patriotism, *sanin ya kamata*, self-discipline, *ladabi* politeness, *natsuwa* calmness, *naciya* persistence, *gwani* expert, *fasihi* eloquence, *haziKi* quick intelligence in language and in his endeavors. With these, Muhammad (1997) considers late Ibrahim Yaro Yahaya as being rooted in the minds' of people throughout his life and the longer one stays with him the better he rooted deep in his mind because he was simple, cheerful, who loved people and he was loved by the people.

Kirk-Greene (2000) also describes a hero and heroic qualities as being important worldwide. He adds that a good man (in the Western tradition) is recognized by being gentle and noble, as well as emulating supreme qualities; such as truth, courage, devotion to duty, sympathy for the protection of the weak, kindness, unselfishness, and fellowship. *Mutumun kirki* and *kirki* 'upright' rely upon *hali* 'character' in Hausa. One can be judged by his action and by his physical character, though inner quality of a man (lionhearted hero) cannot turn him to good man. *Mutumun kirki* is regarded as a hero based on his constant speaking *Gaskiya* 'truth' as a matter of character and principle in his life. The second reputation is *amana* 'trust'. A good man is trusted; due to his ability to keep one's secret as well as safe protection of whatsoever given to him. The writer realizes that *gaskiya* and *amana* are important in guiding Hausa children as well as in people's daily routine. Whoever does *gaskiya* and *amana* is expecting reward in this world and on the Day of Judgment. *Karamci* 'open handed generosity' is the third quality of *mutumin kirki* that *manya-manya* 'the big shots' are expected to give out to destitute, Kirk-Greene (2000) says whosoever attributes to *karamci* 'open handed generosity' will be named as *mai baiwa* 'he who gives freely,' and an utmost respect is given to him because he gives out money and kind for *sadaka* 'the alms', for God sake and for *tausayi* 'sympathy' to humanity. *Hakuri* 'patience' plays a vital role in Hausa daily life, it is frequently used in proverbs, poems, fables and daily conversations because it remedies any critical condition that one finds himself, indeed, Hausa fate relies on *hakuri* 'patience'. *Hankali* distinct *mutumin kirki* with sound and mature judgment, it helps him to behave decently and to utter the right statement in the right place and at the right time. Certainly, it is controlling him to be cautious in his affairs. *Kunya* 'shame' is the quality of a good man; the meaning of *kunya* is far ahead of English meaning (shame). *Mutumun kirki* shuns any shameless act; be it utterance or action to maintain his dignity, though it is a waste of time to shy a shameless man and it is preferable to leave a child with debt than disgrace (*kunya*). Likewise, *ladabi* 'courtesy' is attributed to a good man as Kirk-Greene (2000) points out that, it is a personal manner and respect to aged people, *malam* 'teacher', *alkalai* 'judge' and *sarki* 'chief'; it is normally the manner given to superiors by the inferior one(s), which distinct *mutunci*; *mutunci* is the ability to know the dignity of human beings whether they are inferior or superior and *mutunci* is normally comes from the superior to the inferior and a good man always avoids insult and *cin mutuncin* 'humiliation' over people. *Hikima* 'wisdom' and *adalci* 'scrupulous behavior' are the last two features of *mutumin kirki* which are associated with age and Islamic education. A leader who attributed to these qualities (wisdom and justice) considers as *mutumin kirki*, also *kirki* and *adalci* are identical; another meaning of *adali* is God fearing. Finally, *fara'a* 'coherent' and *haiba* 'respect' or *kwarjini* are attached to good man based on his kind to humanity.

Kirk-Greene (2000) observes the attributes of moral virtue in *Makau* such as *kunya*, *amana*, *hakuri*, trust in God etc, and in the novel *Shaihu Umar* the students of *Shaihu Umar* (a character) testify to his excellent virtues of being a saint that people said. Furthermore, *Abubakar Tafawa Balewa* (the author) has the standards of *mutumin kirki* too. The writer examines *tarbiyya* exist in Hausa proverbs, verses, folktales, *kirari*, and also *masu sarauta* are recognized as the role models in Hausaland. Muhammadu Rumfa requested *Al-magili* to write a guide for him specifically on his personal and official affairs. The writer overviews the primary responsibility

of the Muslim Hausa family for teaching virtue to their children, *kunya*, *hankali* and *ladabi* as well as emulating good character throughout life and the Qur'anic school assisted in teaching Islamic principles. Kirk-Greene (2000) examines Emir of Kano Abdullahi Burja was liberal, eloquent, wise and magnanimous. Emir of *Kano Tsamía* was known with courage and dignity. Muhammadu Rumfa (1463-1499) was also a good man, a just and learned who was associated with Ibrahim Dabo due to his administrative justice. Dabo too was an erudite scholar and pious who protected his subjects accordingly. In addition, Muhammadu Dikko (1906-1944) was generous to his people in Katsina, he had given deep concerned to moral education to his children. The writer adds that, *haiba*, *farin jini* 'popularity', outstanding patience, gentleness of behavior are the attributes of Emir Abdullahi Bayero who was a scholar that steadfast on *ladabi* and Qur'anic education to his children. Muhammadu Bello (1817-1837) is regarded as one of the greatest Sultan in Hausa due to his fear of God, respectability and steadfast on Shehu dan Fodio's way.

Amin (2002) also depicts life as being transient, very hard, complex, capricious, deceptive, haphazard, enjoyable, didactic, dirty, attractive, contemptible, subduing, hierarchical and fastidious in Hausa thought. He adds that *zaman lafiya* 'peaceful living' as the main aim of Hausa people, to live in peace one has to cling for knowledge, patience, perseverance, honesty, caution, resoluteness, hard work, contentment, goodness and virtuosity, obedience, respectability, love for close relations, communality and mutual assistance and one has to realize their changing role. In addition, a virtuous is recognized with virtues such as *tawali'u* humility, *dattako* respectability, *kamun kai* dignity, *saukin kai* simplicity and *yakana* contentment. Kamusun Hausa (2006), Newman (1997), Bargery (1993) and Abraham (1978) describe *sauki* means ease and simple while Bargery (1993) says *saukin kai* is associated with amenable to advice and not to self-opinionated, Abraham (1978) says *sauki* is attributed to lightness, easiness while *saukin kai* or *saukin dabi'a* means tractable, amenable, and I forgiveness. Lexicographers in Hausa say *tawali'u* means humility means, that is one to show humility, Bargery (1993) and Abraham (1978) said that both *tawali'u* means humility, *tawakkali* resigning oneself or bowing to what is considered the will of God or submissiveness to God's hands whereas Kamusun Hausa (2006) attributes *tawali'u* with *kan kantar da kai* means to be simple. Abraham (1978) sees *dattako* mean being respectable, sound judgment and to behave with dignity, for Newman (1997) *dattako* has to do with dignity (respect humility), it is also in line with *mutunci* decency, *kamala* prestige, *martaba* rank. In other words, respect is associated with politeness as well *ladabi*, *biyayya*, *girmamawa*, *ban girma*, *daraja*, and *mutuntawa*. Moreover, self-respect means *mutunci*, one is also respected for his knowledge, and religion. *Mai halin dattijo* and *dattijantaka*, mean respectable while *mai ladabi* and *mai kunya* mean respectful. Bargery (1993) says *dattako* is derived from *dattijo* which means reliability; hence poise character that one would expect from an elder and can be found in young or old. Kamusun Hausa (2006), Bargery (1993) and Abraham (1978) describe *yakana* is synonymous with *kana'a*, *wadar zuci*, *wada*, *da'a*, *sanin yakamata* and *jin nauyi ko kunya*. *Yakana* means contentment, complacency, serenity, knowing what is right, proper, and befitting.

The views on virtues by Hausa scholars and moral philosophers suggest that humility and modesty are synonymous which involve shame, shyness, moderation, simplicity, self-consciousness, reserve, calmness among others. A virtuous Hausa man is benevolent, generous and friendly, his faith guides modesty in him and each one increases one another. The modest Hausa man dresses appropriately, speak appropriately and live in harmony with humanity. He is magnanimous to everyone and chooses friends or companions carefully. The review of literature portrays significance of Islam to humility and modesty in Hausa culture as well as their aim to live in peace and harmony which donate to virtue and inculcation of moral values before the children. Islamic knowledge and age play a role for one to become wise and render

justice. Although reviewed materials enumerate virtues but did not examine the incorporation of self-awareness and open-mindedness to humility and modesty in Hausa verse, while this paper overviews humility and modesty in Hausa verse are incorporated self-awareness and open-mindedness among others.

HAUSA VERSE

Beckson, K. and Ganz, A. (1972) says that a verse is a metrical line in poetry and poetry is different from verse, while Baldick, C. (2004) describes verse as metrical and rhythmic line of poetry, he also says that a stanza can be called a verse and poetry can also answer the name of a verse. Muhammad, D. (1977) distinguishes between oral song (*waka I*) and written poetry, he says that composition and performance are accompanied with *waka I*, it is also composed for a patron and audience are required to disseminate it before them. Oral song is accompanied with music and with or without choral response. *Waka I* has fixed tune and metrical freedom, the stanza of oral song has no regular line pattern, and repetition is one of the features of oral song. It is uncommon for oral song to begin and end with opening and closing doxologies as well Arabicaisms, but *waka I* has great influence on *waka II* particularly the rhythm and refrain in *Akilu's* art.

Bello (1978) examines themes, form and style of Hausa written poetry, he emphasizes on the significance of rhythm while composing both oral and written poems, he then explains written Hausa poetry borrowed thirteen meters from Arabic poetry (Kamil, Madid, Basid, Wafir, Dawil, Hajaz, Rajaz, Ramal, Munsarih, Hafif, MuKutalib, Mutadarab and Mutadarak) respectively. The researcher discusses segmental rhyme as one among the features of Hausa written poetry which comprises both internal and external rhymes and the structure of stanza in Hausa poems are gauruwa, 'yar tagwai, Kwar uku, 'Yar huɗu, 'Yar biyar, Tahamisi and Tarbi'i. Bello (1978) observes the existence of opening and closing doxologies in Hausa poetry as well as Arabicaism, simplicity, and the use of figures of speech among others. Muhammad (1977) also surveys segmental rhyme and tonal rhyme are the features of written poetry and proves that tonal rhyme exists in both oral and written Hausa poetry. He then studies tonal running rhyme, tonal internal rhyme in *Akilu's* poem and compares *Akilu's* poems with other poets, he then proceeds to prosodic rhythmic and examines the language employed by *Akilu* in his art where he observes *Sokoto* dialect, assimilation of the short feminine possessive link etc. The researcher examines morphological variation, tense/aspect from *Akilu's* composition as well as run-on and enjambment. Muhammad (1977) overviews rhetorical pattern from different perspective in *Akilu's* poems and examines figures of speech employed by the artist (simile, symbolism, allegory and metaphor). Then Sa'id (1978) enumerates Hausa jihad poetry concentrate more on religious matters as they discuss mainly on social, political, mysticism and astronomy.

It is known to scholars about the significance of Arabic melody and Islamic influence to Hausa verse, not only written poetry but the oral songs, this paper studies humility and modesty and the incorporation of self-awareness and open-mindedness to them in Hausa verse rather than studying the form, style or theme but the examination relies on theme, form and style, though it concentrates on virtues as examines in Hausa verse (written poetry).

HUMILITY AND MODESTY

Hausa verse delights and instructs while instructing it develops human personality to be self-discipline, resolute, faithful, and benevolent, as a virtue, modesty is contrary to vice as it is guiding humankind to emulate righteousness and become diligent and persistent to morality. Humility in Hausa verse incorporates other virtues as it goes hand in hand with modesty and redirects attitudes of benevolent to honor God the creator and his messenger and be

intermediary with other people. The verse illuminates boastfulness is vice as the review of literature outlines good man in Hausa possesses virtues from childhood through his parents, Qur'anic school and other genres of orature and literature inculcate morality to them and elites are also regarded as role models because their affairs is attributed to moral principles. With this, Hausa verse inculcates humility and modesty for the development of spiritual values as Muhammadu Bello warns thus in *'Yan Jihadi*:

<p><i>Makumyaci mai iya kau da rai nan, Shi anka yas ba a cikin batu nai. Sun jirkice sun saki masu dauri, Son zucciya shi aka bi da guri.. Ban fid da kaina ba ina cikinsu, Aikin ga duk ban wuce dai gare su. Aikinmu na mu duka sai wa dansu, Guda-guda sunka iya ma kansu. Sun bi ma Allah ga abin da yac ce, Foro hani safe zuwa marece. Su bi shi kullum ba su karkace ba, Da karkacewassu ka dan sun tuba. Na tuba Allah bisa 'yan ayyuka, Da babu kyau su nika wani kuka. Dare da rana duka ban kula ba, Cikin hawan nafsi ina zunuba. Allah shi gafarta abin da niy yi, Kurakuraina duka in ji sanyi. Daidaita aikinmu zuwa ga Sunna, Ku jama'a mu duka Muslimina. Allah shi kefe mu shi ba mu iko, Tuba ga Allah mu fice ma tarko. Kowa ka son gobe shi samu tsira, Shi tuba tun yanzu akwai dihara. Shina da rai ya ki barin zunuba, Shi ta shiri gobe na shan azaba.</i></p>	<p>A reserved person who calms for temptation People turn against him They deviate from the right way Rather, egotism is well respected I am inclusive among them I practice as deviate as they do We have to strengthen our faith But only few they strive to right path They are obedient to the will of God They are steadfast day and night None of them denigrate the truth They repent to God instantly the defame O, God! I repent though I am ingratitude I admonish despite my little obedient to you I relegate your way day and night I run away from teaching of the Qur'an O, Allah forgive my shortcomings For me to be in your mercy O, God guide our affairs to Prophetic tradition O, the Muslim community We pray for Allah to guide us Following the right direction is the best Whoever wants to be in the paradise He has to seek for forgiveness to Allah If one enjoy the sinful while he is alive For sure, blazing of fire should be his abode</p>
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The author portrays moral bankrupt as such as pride, arrogance, shamelessness, disregarding clerics among others in his composition titled *'Yan Jihadi* whereby he desensitizes immorality and warns people who absorbed evil as an order of the day. Out of modesty, self-awareness, open-mindedness and courtesy of Muhammadu Bello whom identities, strengths and limitations of his society motivate him to admonish himself and society to be righteousness and adhere the teachings of righteous scholars. The verse appreciates self-egotism in the society ravages minds to appreciate knowledge and Islamic guidance where their selfishness closed eyes and ears to accept the truth and considered clerics and their teachings archaic except few among the citizens who trust teachings of Islam. Out of courtesy and self-incrimination of Muhammadu Bello been among the leading clerics of the time he incriminates himself as humankind and repents instantly; which been humble and modest to God and his Prophet also been an erudite scholar who admonishes systematically and revives Islamic culture to the populace. His persistence to repent to Allah is an advice to other people and himself to escape punishment on the Day of Resurrection. With modesty and erudition Abdullahi Bin Fodio also applies similar method in admonishing Bawa Jangwarzo in his composition titled *Wa'azu Ga Sarkin Gobir Bawa*. Bawa been the leader of the then Gobir with his subjects to submit themselves in modesty before Allah as he says:

Ba bisa na ba kai jiya,

Kama addin da gaskiya,

Ya da wada da dariya,

Kul fa ka ji su ka fiya,

Ka zuba kanka gobara.

Ai ta bin wanda ya isa,

Wanda yash shimfi da kasa,

Baya ya gina can bisa,

Wanda bai bi shi ya rasa,

Kai ku zan karba nai kira.

Kama halshe hawai hawa,

Tsari idanu da kunnuwa,

Tsari ciki duk da hannuwa,

Tsari kafafu hawai suwa,

Inda wasa yi hattara.

O, you listen I am not an attendant to the court of an emir

Follow the religion with trust

Avoid the dwarf with wisdom

I warn you not to be obedient to them

You will be in the great punishment

Be obedient to God alone

Who spread the earth

Who created the heaven also

There is lost in disobeying Allah

O, you listen to warn I made

Be modest in your utterances

Lower your gaze and guard your ears

Protect your stomach and your hands

Regulate places you visit

Be guided with lure of this world

The verse speaks to dignitary and ignobility out of courtesy and modesty to believe in the oneness of Allah and addresses the leadership of Gobir; under Bawa Jangwarzo to trust Islam as a guide to humanity as religion and abide by its teaching or otherwise on the Day of resurrection. The author continues to admonish the leader or everyone who has power to understand that Allah creates the universe, he separates heaven and earth while they were together and he is the one deserves to be worship alone. In other words, the author invites both the leader of Gobir and the subjects to be sensitive and self-discipline because there is humility and modesty in what to say with the tongue, what to see with the eyes, what to hear with the ears, what to eat in the stomach, what to do with the hands and where to go with the legs. Indeed, humility and modesty are the characteristics of Islam and affected by social, economic and political activities. With this Abdullahi Bin Fodio figures out method of enthroning a king thus in the following stanzas:

Saraki su ka karfafa fada za be,

Ga 'yan sarkinsu wane su juye suna.

A ce sarki a ba shi abin sarauta,

Su zuzzuge gaisuwa da kiɗi na murna.

Ga al'adunsu kowaz zo shi duka,

Wadansu suna afi ku ji wane dai na.

Su gangumma da algaitu kalangai,

Da tamburra abin wasa na sunna.

Da jan kaya da gwarje alharini,

Azurfa su abin girmansu ke nan.

Barori ag gare su da 'yan barade,

Lifidda ba su tarac cin amana.

Chiefs have power and influence in the palace

That led to change enthronement

Once the new emir is crown

They celebrate in singing and praising

Bowing down is a tradition to a

King

Putting ashes on the head before the king is

part of the culture, I warn so-and-so

Drums, reed wind-instrument, hourglass-

shaped drum

And tambourine are played against the sunna

They wear silk garment and drawn to ground

They adorn themselves with silver

They have servants, mounted men

(horsemen)

Quilted protection for horse and they are

distrust

Awareness and open-mindedness of the poet criticize immodesty and boastfulness in leadership; he critiques spiritual bankrupt, absence of both inner and outer modesty in the appearance of a leader as he adorns himself with things that are forbidden clothes as such it is prohibited for men to wear silk garment in Islam. He censures traditional robe as he describes

the enthroned king wears inappropriate garment that touches earth. The verse condemns method of choosing a leader by kingmakers who nominate as like, followers bow down as an allegiance to the enthroned king, in Hausa tradition required praise singers follow with singing using different musical instruments (drums, reed wind-instrument, hourglass-shaped drum and tambourine) to the enthroned king respectively. The verse disregards a tradition in contrary to modesty of Islam because it negates trust, fairness and justice. Whereas erudition in scholarship, humility and modesty among other virtues were celebrated in most of the 19th century Hausa poems as Shehu Bin Fodio manifests thus in the following stanzas:

<i>Kwaj ja adawa da sarki Walla ba ni ciki</i>	Whoever hated the chief, I swear was not among them
<i>Kwaj ja sarauta ga sarki walla ba ni ciki,</i>	Whoever disgust authority of the chief I swear was not among them
<i>Ni ban zuwa fada ba ko zan shiga ba ciki,</i>	I was not in the palace, I will not engage into the matter
<i>Alhamdu Lillahi kowa ya ji ba ni ciki,</i>	Praise be to Allah everyone testify that I am into the matter
<i>Ga batun sarauta duka Wallahi Wallahi.</i>	I am off to all leadership activity I swear
<i>Mai son Ta'ala shi yo ilmi shi san shi kwarai,</i>	Those who believe in Allah should strive to acquire for knowledge
<i>Mai son Ta'ala shi yo salla shi san shi kwarai,</i>	Those who believe in Allah should stand firm in saying salat and know its conditions
<i>Kwas so Fiyayyae shina so nai mu so shi kwarai,</i>	Whoever embraced tradition of the best of mankind we should be fair over his affairs
<i>Sunnan ta Annabi hanya ta ku santa kwarai</i>	Sunna (Prophetic tradition) is to be learn with keenness
<i>Kowa fa yab bi ta ya unfaana Wallahi.</i>	Whoever follows the sunna is safe I swear

The modesty in Shehu Bin Fodio did not allow him to associate himself with power and vice, rather dissociates from leadership as well as going to the palace been the leading scholar, he emits to leadership of Gobir apparently and guides the society to mediate and be modest to Allah through constant prayers and acquire the true knowledge of Islam on how to conduct prayers as well as religious activities in accordance to the teaching of the Prophet. He then encourages the society to persist on the way of Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) for salvation on the earth and in the hereafter. With such utterances, Shehu is modest in guiding humanity and in relating to the authority of Gobir out of courtesy he proposes whomever listening to their teaching required humility to God, to Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.) for happy ending. Humility, modesty and erudition are apparent in Hausa verse as Abdullahi Bin Fodio warns kingmakers in the following stanzas thus:

<i>Ku saurara gabatam musulmina,</i>	O, Muslim leaders listen
<i>Ku bi ta ku bar sarautak kafirina.</i>	Dissociate from leadership which is not in accordance with Islam
<i>Musulmi manya-manya da salihansu,</i>	Muslims who are elders and pious
<i>Ka za ben mai gabatat muslimina</i>	Discuss on whom will govern Islamic state
<i>Su taru su dauki alwashi na da'a,</i>	They pay allegiance to him
<i>Ga foron nan na Alkur'an da Sunna.</i>	As it is ordained in the Qur'an and Sunna

The poet enumerates the Islamic method of enthroning a king or a leader which assigned duty to magnanimous scholars to decide a right leader; they should be obedient to his leadership and respect his authority after the enthronement. The first stanza reinforces learned to discharge their duty in accordance with the Islamic guide which is different from traditional method of

enthronement in Hausa tradition. In addition, humility and modesty guide erudition of the poet in revealing truth that modesty is as an attitude of mind displayed by a person and shows his relationship with God and prophetic way as well as his interaction with other people. Hausa verse enumerates behavior and relationship from different perspective but it is guided by God and believes in oneness of God, his prophetic way is also recognized and human affairs are guided by humility as the verse displays imaginable world created by the author who demonstrates inner and outer modesty across humanity. Moreover, Hausa verse engulfs humility and modesty in opening and closing doxology, the doxology in many compositions of Hausa verse instructs and guides personality to believe in the oneness of God. It is also a known tradition in Hausa to thank God in the beginning and the ending of whichever activity which is driven from the teaching of Islam. The prominent *Sa'adu Zungur's Arewa Jumhuriya ko Mulukiya?* is by the culture which theology overwhelms thus in the opening doxology as follows:

<p><i>Sai mu gode Allah shi dāya, Don shine Sarkin gaskiya. Ya mallaki dukkan talikai, Na kwari da tudu da samaniya.</i></p> <p><i>Da mutum, aljan da mala'ika, Dabbar sarari da ta maliya. Mulki, iko daula duka, Na ga Sarki Allah shi dāya. Shi ya ke ba wanda ya so duka, Ya sarautu a lardin duniya. Shi ya ke karɓe ta ga taliki, Don ya dāndani wahalar duniya. Shi ka girmama wanda ya so duka, Shi ka sanya wa dānsu su sha wuya. Shi ka cusa dare a cikin wuni, Kuma ya zaro hasken safiya. Shi ka rayawar mamaci duka, Shi ke kashe mai rai, shi dāya. Ikonsa a kan kome ya ke, A ruwa da tudu da samaniya. Alwakilu, mu dogara duk garai, Zahirinmu da boye a zuciya.</i></p>	<p>We should thank Allah alone For He is the true King He controls all beings Valley dwellers, highlanders and those in the skies The Human, the Jinn and the Angels Animals on the land and sea Power, authority and domain—all Are with Allah, the only King It is He who guides to whom He likes So that he leads in worldly affairs He confiscates it from anybody So that he suffers the burdens of the world It is He who exalts whom he likes And make others suffer He causes the night to pass into the day And spins the morning light He resurrects the dead And kills the living. He alone His power is over everything In the sea, the land and the skies The Trustee, we should depend on Him Overtly and covertly in our hearts (Yakubu, 1999, Pp.337-339)</p>
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The last line of the last stanza illuminates if the heart is guided and purified the character would develop humility and modesty of humankind would trust and believe in the oneness of God who owns the universe and directs its affairs without a helper, he controls day and night, he gives life and takes it accordingly. The opening doxology admonishes that God provides to his creature and tests them in affluence and poverty; he enthrones and dethrones human beings as a test. Despite the fact that the verse was written in the 20th century it maintains the ethics of the 19th century tradition where modesty guides erudition of the poet in the whole stanzas by guiding audiences' spiritual development in humility and modesty to oneness of God and to honor the bestowed he rendered to humanity. The author invites humanity to honor the greatness and the uniqueness of Allah for the shelter provided on earth and encourages humankind to act righteous and renders justice to biodiversity.

SELF-AWARENESS

Hausa verse utilizes both moral and intellectual virtues and portrays the wisdom of a poet and his ability to illuminate and educate society on a particular issue or matter. Poets enjoin moral and intellectual virtues as humility and modesty required self-awareness Hausa verse also enumerates self-awareness of a poet while trying to create *nagari* or *mutumin kirki*, the poet assessed his identity, strength and limitation to enable him to justify between the right and the wrong objectively and act accordingly. Humility and modesty describe a character, his noble decision and breakthrough, as they do these they are also encouraging self-awareness of the benevolent to meet up the end result as Ummaru Nassarawa Wazirin Gwandu's self-awareness portrays thus in the following example:

*Sadda duk bukata tak kam min,
Ko da yaushe na ko taf far min,
Sai gare ka don ka daukam min,
Naka alƙawal bai saɓawa.
Ga abin da hali yak kawo,
An yi dauri yau kuma ya dawo,
Na ƙudurta guri na sawo,
Kadirun nufe ni da dacewa.*

*Dauri anka kasan, nid daure,
Anka koma kasan, nij jimre,
Yanzu hankurina ya ƙare,
Kadirun nufan ni da ramawa.*

*Masu kokuwa duk sun shirya,
Ga shi har fagen yi an shaya,
Ga ni ban da karfo ko laya,
Ga ni ko ina son kayaswa.
Wansu sun yi gayya can su ko,
Sun yi taulahi an amsa ko,
Ni fa ga ni nan cirko-cirko,
Agajinka dai nika dubowa.
Ga su wane can wai sun kimtsa,
'Yan farofaganda sun watsa,
Duk cikin ƙasashe sun kutsa,
Wai batunsu dai suka gyarawa.
Jalla kai da kay yi su ka fi su,
Kai ka walwale mini dankensu,
Kuma ka mallake mini kowansu,
Duk su zan garan suka komowa.
Tun da ban da kowa baicin ka,
Ya Halimu yo min ranarka,
Al-Alimu ga dan bayinka,*

Yasshe babu duk mai tsintowa

Whenever I am in need,
At all the time if I required something
You promise to sustain my need
I am assured your promise will fulfill
Here is the current event
It had happened then repeating itself
My intention is to contest
O. Kadirun (The possessor of power and
authority) made me the winner
I lost the first contesting
I lost the second contending
I am impatient this time
O, Kadirun (The possessor of power and
authority) made me the winner
The wrestles are ready
The wrestling space is encircled
I am not rely on amulet and charm
O, God I want to be the winner
Other contenders invited people
They are adopted successfully
I am now standstill
Waiting for your assistance
Here is so (person) is ready
Propagandist spread information
They went over the land
To lure people
O, the God you are the Lord of humankind
You are to unravel their knot
You are to retain them for me
All of them to vote for me
I have no god other than You (Allah)
O, Halim (The Forbearing) restrain on me
O, Al-Alim (The All-Knowing) here is the
son of you servants
Thrown out nobody cares about
Him

The famous *Zaɓaɓɓiya* of Ummaru Nassarawa Wazirin Gwandu attributes modesty in the author's thought while in the political arena of his era, he weighed himself in comparison to other contenders whom he describes were good at propaganda, and other political intricacies. The tricks of other contenders humbled the author to mediate victory of the incoming election

to Allah not to lose the seat as it happened two times in the past. Despite the eagerness of the poet to win the seat but his self-discipline and awareness control his emotion, they guide him to lower himself in appropriate language, although abusive language is common to opponents in political jingles, rather the poet intercedes with different attributes of Allah to win. In other words, the poet is humble where he uses decorous language for God to intervene in to the matter, he then instructs others to do the same and elaborates that the campaign strategies of other contenders was against the religious culture although he did not mention the name of all of them out of courtesy but he persists on theology and believe in oneness of God.

OPEN-MINDEDNESS

Hausa verse describes the benevolent as modest and humble in his affairs, he incorporates self-awareness, self-discipline and open-minded in his activity, his curiosity and self-understanding as well as knowing others alert him to see beyond his control, he approaches events and activities with wisdom and be bold because he rates the fault or weaknesses. His mission is to correct the world. The previous examples explore the incorporation of self-awareness to modesty and humility in Hausa verse as the below example discloses the incorporation of open-mindedness in humility and modesty where the verses say:

<i>Na ji arashin 'yan gijibirci,</i>	I understand irony by ridiculers
<i>Ban kula da su masu habaici,</i>	I do not care with mockers
<i>Ban bugun gaban jin Turanci,</i>	I cannot boast of fluency in spoken English
<i>Bai zama dalilin kamawa.</i>	I cannot believe in these too
<i>Ban bugun gaban wai na waye,</i>	I cannot feel proud that I am famous
<i>Ban yi duk tsimi ba da niƙ ɓoye,</i>	I have not save amass wealth
<i>Ni ga Jalla nib biɗi rinjaye,</i>	Allah is to take care of me
<i>Jinkayinsa shi aw wayewa.</i>	His mercy is my wisdom
<i>Ban aminta inda mutum duk ba,</i>	I have no trust in humankind
<i>Gun biyan bukata ko ɗai ba,</i>	Regarding my success whatsoever it is
<i>Ko kaɗan mutum bai kai can ba,</i>	Humankind is imperfect for that
<i>Duk da tashi bai iya ganewa.</i>	He is weak to know his fate also
<i>Wanda an yi dauri gabaninai,</i>	He fails to know the past events
<i>Za a koma yi kuma bayanai,</i>	There would be other events after him
<i>Wanda anka tabbata farkonai,</i>	Humankind has the beginning
<i>Anka tabbata zai karewa.</i>	It has been ordained death for humankind
<i>Wanda bai wuce shi yi kwana ba,</i>	Humankind falls asleep
<i>Bai wuce shi mance abinai ba,</i>	He can forget anything related him
<i>Wanda bai sanam ma rabonai ba,</i>	He is unable to know his fate
<i>Yaushe za shi gane min nawa?</i>	How can that person be able to remedy my problems?

The above example incorporates open-mindedness to humility and modesty as the poet challenges fetishism audaciously. The method of warning for people to disregard culture of mediation to humankind on their worldly shows brevity and modesty to open up to the wrongness of the people; it also signifies self-reflection and associating self with culture. The poet's dissociation to fetishism and downsizing human quality in comparison with the God reveals that humility and modesty are incorporated with open-mindedness. The verse narrows down the humankind as a weak creature because he is created by the Lord which means that he has the beginning and the ending (he dies), humankind sleeps, forgets the past and he does not have the ability to prove what is ordained in the future except Allah who is in the absolute control of everything and nothing escapes from him. The incorporation of open-mindedness to humility and modesty guide the author to enlighten his society to discriminate between the power of God and the weakness of humankind. Despite the fact that he critiques the weakness

in humankind but he recognizes humankind is bestowed with knowledge and wisdom which humility and modesty control the author to be self-esteem as he mention some of his quality wisely instead to brag with fluency in spoken English and ability to know modern knowledge before his opponents, he prefers to be humble and spoke to them wisely that he was aware of their political atrocities which would not intimidate him rather he mediate to God.

CONCLUSION

Virtue as a trait of character is promoted in Hausa verse, the verse lowers arrogance and pride to the populace, through self-incrimination and admonishment by the poets. Hausa Islamic verse persists on the oneness of God and recommends the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.). The corpus poems desensitize immorality and create imagining utilitarian state through the endowed knowledge and wisdom of the poets. The poems incorporate virtues and admonish both teachers and leaders to lead the followers accordingly. The paper discusses aristocratic arrogance and spiritual bankrupt of people in pre-jihad Hausa society, as well as egotism, shamelessness and disrespect to the clerics' reform. The study exposes coercion in political arena of the 20th century Hausaland where the corpus poems call for replacement of vice with good virtue of humility and modesty. Apart from humility and modesty appraises in the study, the poets demands society be benevolent by imbibing other virtues such as simplicity, truthfulness, trust and trustworthiness, generosity, wisdom and knowledge. His trust in God and following prophetic tradition as well as his good relationship with other people would be of immense benefit to everyone

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